

A PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON MEDICATIONS PRESCRIBED AND DOSAGE ADJUSTMENT IN PATIENTS WITH RENAL IMPAIRMENT AT A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Background: In individuals with renal impairment, the wrong medicine dosage might result in toxicity or ineffective treatment. Patients are at a significant risk of experiencing associated adverse events due to drug interactions when polypharmacy is utilized to treat comorbid diseases. This calls for suitable changes to the renal dosage. **Aim & Objectives:** This study aims to study prescription patterns and dosage adjustments for medications in patients with renal impairment. **Materials & Methods:** It is a prospective and observational study done over a period of six months in Osmania general hospital at a tertiary care teaching hospital, study included patients of either sex, patients above 18 years, patients diagnosed with renal impairment, patients with confirmed diagnosis of AKI and CKD. Whereas pregnant and lactating mothers, patient with a gap in their medical history, cancer and covid patients and patients with other disease, and patient is regarded to be morbid are excluded from the study. **Results:** In

our study of 110 patients, most patients were Male (60%) & Female (40%). With age between 50-59 were found to be more effected. The most common risk factor and comorbidities was

found to be hypertension (74%) diabetes mellitus (51%), a large number of patients are suffering from stage 5 of ckd (52%), stage 4 ckd (31%) followed by other stages which is classified by KDOQI classification. Based on the rifle criteria classification (54.54%) patients comes in the category of failure followed by, (20.90%) patients fall in the category of ESRD. Majority of patients serum creatinine was found to be in between 4.1-6.0mg/dl. There was significant decrease in EGFR was noted and majority were found to be in between 0-10% of EGFR. According to Cockcroft gault formula for estimating creatinine clearance (25.45%) patients were adjusted for the dose and not adjusted was (0.90%) and others doesn't require dosage adjustment. The prescribing patterns of drugs were antihypertensives, antidiabetic, diuretics, antibiotics, proton pump inhibitor, anemic drugs, antacids, antiplatelets etc. The most prescribed drug was loop diuretic. **Conclusion:** This study examines prescription patterns and dosage adjustments for medications in patients with renal impairment, and drug interactions in prescription and focusing on those aged 18 and above. The findings highlight the significance of individualized treatment approaches in optimizing therapeutic success while minimizing potential hazards. More study and collaboration among healthcare experts could result in better medication management guidelines for patients with renal impairment.

KEYWORDS: Creatinine clearance, Chronic kidney disease, Dose adjustment, Kidney failure, Renal impairment.

INTRODUCTION

Kidney is the vital organ for maintaining homeostasis of electrolytes and fluids. It plays a major role in the metabolism of many drugs.^[1]

Renal impairment is a condition where the kidney cannot remove or eliminate the toxic substances enough from the body. Acute kidney injury is a sudden (within 48 hours) reduction in kidney function, with an absolute increase in serum creatinine of $>_0.3$ mg/dl or 50% increase in serum creatinine from base line. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is defined as $FR <_60$ ml/min with marked kidney damage or both for more than 3 months duration both AKI and CKD have an effect on multiple organs. In patients with renal impairment the harmful effects of drugs are poorly tolerated. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account dose adjustment of drugs in a standard manner.^[2]

The break down and elimination of many drugs and pharmacologically active metabolites depends on normal kidney function. The renal elimination of drugs and its active metabolites

are impaired in patients with renal impairment which causes accumulation in the body. The significant reduction in plasma protein binding of drugs could influence the pharmacokinetic procedure of distribution and elimination. Various drug metabolizing enzymes and drug transporters activity has been declined in chronic renal failure. Drug dosing errors are the most major drug related problems in the renal dysfunction patients, incorrect dosing causes toxic or ineffective therapy in kidney impairment patients. In addition, older patients are at a higher risk of developing adverse events caused by decline in renal function and with the use of multiple drugs to tolerate co-morbid conditions. Accumulation of drug and toxicity can develop progressively if dosage adjustment is not made in renally impaired patient. The glomerular filtration associate with elimination of drug by kidney, thus it is necessary to use eGFR or eCrcl for dose adjustment in patients with renal impairment. The Cockcroft-Gault (CG) equation provides an approximate of creatinine clearance, an apparently slight increase in serum creatinine can display a noticeable fall in GFR, using validated formula is compulsory for the calculation of Crcl and or eGFR in every patient.^[3]

Chronic kidney disease has become global health and economic burden, an approximate 5-10 million people every year effects from kidney disease, the ineffective doses in hospitalized patients can prolong the duration of hospitalization and cost of the treatment.^[4]

Therefore, the dose adjustment should be made either by decreasing the dose or prolong the interval of administration.^[2]

OBJECTIVES

- To analyze the prescribing patterns for drugs and doses in patients with kidney disease.
- To record and analyze the dosage adjustments done on various drugs in the kidney disease patients.
- To identify the drug interactions in the prescriptions of kidney disease patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a Prospective observational study approved by Institutional Ethics Committee (Reg No. MCP/IEC/PD/PR/78). This study was carried out at Osmania General Hospital, a tertiary care teaching hospital in Hyderabad to evaluate a study on medications prescribed and dosage adjustment in renal impairment patients. Data was gathered over a six-months period from a sample size of 110 patients using a well-prepared data collecting form to methodically compile pertinent information. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics

Committee (IEC) to guarantee that patient confidentiality and ethical standards are followed. Careful data collection was carried out in accordance with the specifications and design of the study. Data were collected from a variety of sources, counseling sessions with patients and their attendees, opinions from doctors and other healthcare professionals, and data from laboratory and radiological tests. Following extensive documentation and entry into Microsoft Excel Spreadsheets, the data was subsequently subjected to additional analysis.

Study Design- A Prospective Observational study

Study Location- The study was executed in Osmania General Hospital, a tertiary care teaching hospital.

Study Population- All patients suffering from renal impairment attending the General Medicine Department and Nephrology OPD of Osmania General Hospital in Hyderabad (Telangana)

Study Duration- 6 months

Sample size- 110.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients of either sex
- Patients above >18 years age
- Patients with confirmed diagnosis of AKI and CKD

Exclusion Criteria

- Pregnant and lactating women's
- Cancer and Covid patients with other disease
- Patient is regarded to be morbid

RESULTS

This study aimed to evaluate medications prescribed and dosage adjustment in patients with renal impairment. The study showed a male predominance (figure 1) and majority in the age range of 50-59 years (figure 2). Hypertension was found to be major risk factor for renal impairment patients (figure 3) most of the patients encountered double co-morbidity (figure 4). Majority of the patients were on stage 5 of CKD (figure 5), according to RFILE Criteria most of the patients suffering AKI and CKD were classified in failure (figure 6) and according to serum Creatinine the range between 4.1-6.0 mg/dl and the EGFR range of 1-

10% was seen predominantly (figure 7 & 8). The total of 28 prescriptions were adjusted for dose and only 1 prescription was not adjusted and other prescriptions dose not required dose adjustment (figure 9). Calcium channel blockers were found to be most prescribed anti-hypertensive drugs in patients with AKI and CKD (figure 10) next insulin was highly prescribed anti-diabetic in renally impaired patients (figure 11) lastly loop diuretics and antibiotics were mostly prescribed (figure 12 & 13). Drug interactions were observed, with Spironolactone and Furosemide frequently implicated. (table 14).

Table 1: DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON GENDER.

GENDER	TOTAL	PERCENTAGE
Male	65	59.09%
Female	45	40.9%

FIGURE 1: REPRESENTING DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON GENDER.

FIGURE 2: REPRESENTING THE DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON AGE.

TABLE 2: DISTRIUTIO DATA BASED ON AGE.

Age Groups	No of Patients	Percentage
18-19	1	0.90%
20-29	5	4.54%
30-39	15	13.63%
40-49	15	13.63%
50-59	31	28.18%
60-69	30	27.27%
70-79	11	10%
80-89	2	1.81%

FIGURE 3: REPRESENTS DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON RISK FACTORS.

TABLE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON RISK FACTORS.

Risk Factor	No of Patients	Percentage (%)
Hypertension	82	74.5%
Diabetes mellitus	57	51.8%
Pyelonephritis	10	9.09%
Obstructive Uropathy	6	5.45%
Renal calculi	3	2.72%

FIGURE 4: REPRESENTING DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON CO-MORBIDITIE.

TABLE 4: DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON CO-MORBIDITIES.

Co-Morbidity	No of Patients	Percentage (%)
Single	24	21.81%
Double	47	42.72%
Multiple	22	20%

FIGURE 5: REPRESENTING DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON CO-MORBIDITIES ENCOUNTERED.

TABLE 5: DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON CO-MORBIDITES ENCOUNTERED.

Co-morbidity	No of Patients	Percentage (%)
Hypertension	82	74.5%
Diabetes mellitus	57	51.81%
Hypothyroidism	8	7.27%
CVA	4	3.63%
Asthma	3	2.72%

FIGURE 6: REPRESENTING KDOQI CLASSIFICATION.

TABLE 6: DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON KDOQI CLASSIFICATION.

Staging	No of Patients	Percentage (%)
Stage 1	2	1.81%
Stage 2	2	1.81%
Stage 3A	3	2.72%
Stage 3B	10	9.09%

Stage 4	35	31.81%
Stage 5	58	52.72%

FIGURE 7: REPRESENTING R.I.F.L. E CRITERIA.

TABLE 7: DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON R.F.I.L.E CRITERIA.

RIFLE CRITERIA	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Risk	3	2.72%
Injury	2	1.81%
Failure	60	54.54%
Loss	1	0.90%
End stage renal disease	23	20.90%

FIGURE 8: REPRESENTING DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON SERUM CREATININE.

TABLE 8: DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON SERUM CREATININ.

SERUM CREATININE (mg/dl)	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
2.0-4.0	27	24.54%
4.1-6.0	34	30.9%
6.1-8.0	8	7.27%
>8.0 mg/dl	30	27.27%

FIGURE 9: REPRESENTING DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON ESTIMATED GFR.

TABLE 9: DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON ESTIMATED GFR.

EGFR(%)	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
0-10%	43	39.09%
11-20%	36	32.72%
21-30%	15	13.63%
31-40%	8	7.27%
>40%	8	7.27%

FIGURE 10: REPRESENTING DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON PRESCRIPTION ADJUSTED FOR DOSE.

TABLE 10: DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON PRESCRIPTION ADJUSTED FOR DOSE.

Dosage Adjustment	No. of Patients	Percentage (%)
Adjusted for Dose	28	25.45%
Not Adjusted	1	0.90%
No adjustment required	81	73.63%

FIGURE 11: REPRESENTING PRESCRIBING PATTERN OF DRUGS WITH HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS.

TABLE 11: PRESCRIBING PATTERN OF DRUGS WITH HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS.

Class of drug	Total no of drugs used	Percentage (%)	DRUGS	TOTAL DRUGS PRESCRIBED	PERCETAGE (%)
Calcium channel Blocker	60	54.54%	Amlodipine	37	33.63%
			Nicardia	14	12.72%
			Nifedipine	8	7.27%
			Cilnidipine	1	0.90%
Beta Blocker	24	21.81%	Metoprolol	20	18.18%
			Cardiolol	2	1.81%
			Labetalol	2	1.81%
Vasodilator	15	13.63%	Arkamin	15	13.63%
ACE-Inhibitor	11	10%	Enalapril	11	10%
Angiotensin receptor Blocker	5	4.54%	Telmisartan	5	4.54%
Alpha-Adrenergic Blocker	1	0.90%	Prazosin	1	0.90%

FIGURE 12: REPRESENTING DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON PRESCRIBING PATTERN OF HYPOGLYCEMIC DRUGS.

TABLE 12: DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON PRESCRIBING PATTERN OF DRUGS WITH DIABETIC PATIENTS.

Class of Drug	Total no Drugs used	Percentage(%)	Drugs	Total Drugs Prescribed	Percentage (%)
Insulin	39	35.45%	Human Mixtard	39	35.45%
Biguanide	7	6.36%	Metformin	7	6.36%
Dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitor	3	2.72%	Vildagliptin	2	1.81%
			Teneligliptin	1	0.90%
SGLT-2 Inhibitor	2	1.81%	Dapagliflozin	2	1.81%
Sulfonylureas	1	0.90%	Glimeperide	1	0.90%

FIGURE 13: REPRESENTING DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ONPRESCRIBING PATTERN OF DRUGS WITH KIDNEY DISEASE.

TABLE 13: DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON PRESCRIBING PATTERN OF DRUGS WITH KIDNEY DISEASE.

Class of Drug	Total no. of Drugs used	Percentage(%)	Drug	Total Drug Prescribed	Percentage (%)
Loop Diuretic	77	70%	Furosemide	77	70%
Potassium sparing Diuretic	16	14.54%	Aldactone	16	14.54%

FIGURE 14: REPRESENTING DISTRIBUTION OF OTHER DRUGSPRESCRIBED.

TABLE 14: DISTRIBUTION OF DATA BASED ON PRESCRIBING PATTERN OF DRUGS WITH KIDNEY DISEASE.

Class of Drug	Total no. of Drugs used	Percentage(%)
Antibiotics	94	85.45%
Proton pump Inhibitor	71	64.54%
Anemic Drugs	63	57.27%
Antacids	44	40%
Anti-Emetic	40	36.36%
Anti-Platelet	24	21.81%
Hyperlipidemic	23	20.90%

TABLE 15: DRUG-DRUG INTERACTION ENCOUNTERED.

Drug Interaction	Effect	Total	Percentage(%)
Spironolactone + Furosemide	Spironolactone increases and Furosemide decreases serum Potassium	13	11.81%
Aspirin + Furosemide	Aspirin increases and Furosemide decreases serum Potassium	13	11.81%
Aspirin + Insulin	Aspirin increases effects of Insulin	9	8.18%
Metoprolol + Furosemide	Metoprolol increases and Furosemide decreases	8	7.27%

	serum Potassium		
Aspirin + Enalapril	Avoid or use alternative result in significant decrease in Renal Function	5	4.54%
Enalapril + Furosemide	Risk of acute Hypotension	5	4.54%
Aspirin + Metoprolol	Both increases serum Potassium; Aspirin decreases effects of Metoprolol	5	4.54%
Metoprolol + Nifedipine	Both increases Anti-Hypertensive channel blocking	4	3.63%
Enalapril + Spironolactone	Risk of Hyperkalemia	4	3.63%
Aspirin + Clopidogrel	Either increases Toxicity of other	4	3.63%
Aspirin + Spironolactone	Aspirin decreases effects of Spironolactone	4	3.63%

DISCUSSION

This study assessed the proportion of appropriately adjusted drugs per patient. In this study, approximately 25.4% prescription dose were adjusted. 0.9% were not adjusted and no adjustment was required for 73.6%. In comparison in Zair Hassan et al. (2021) study, overall, 1,549 drugs were prescribed; 480 (30.99%) drugs required dose adjustment, of which 196 (40.42%) were adjusted properly and the remaining 286 (59.58%) were unadjusted.^[5] factors such as number of drugs requiring adjustment and obstructive nephropathy increased the likelihood of medication dosing errors. While in our observational study most of the drugs were adjusted and other drugs did not require adjustment. Our study also aimed at studying the prescribing patterns of drugs in patients with renal impairment. Our study found similar prescription patterns with Arpit Prajapati et al (2013) study which included cardiovascular drugs, antacids, antibiotics, antidiabetics, anti-emetics and diuretics.^[6] The drugs which were similar among antibiotics were Augmentin, ciprofloxacin, vancomycin, meropenem and among antidiabetics, glimepiride, metformin. Among cardiovascular drugs aspirin, enalapril were common. Diuretics like furosemide were the most common.^[6] In a recent Ousman Abubaker Abdela et al (2021) study, furosemide was the most frequently prescribed medicine type which was used 307 times in 424 enrolled patients. Similarly in our study furosemide was the drug which was the highest prescribed that is 70%. Furosemide is a potent loop diuretic that works to increase the excretion of Na⁺ and water by the kidneys by inhibiting their reabsorption from the proximal and distal tubules, as well as the loop of Henle.^[6] Renal impairment is more prevalent among men than in women. In Ousman Abubaker Abdela et al (2021) study 55% were males whereas females were 45%. In our study 65 cases (59.09%) were males and 45 cases (40.9%) were females.^[2]

In the same study mean age group of affected patients was 60 years while in our study 31 cases were found in the age group of 50-59 followed by 30 cases in the age group of 60-69.

Although the MDRD equation is widely used to estimate GFR in many parts of the world, we used the Cockcroft Gault formula.

CONCLUSION

This study examines prescription patterns and dosage adjustments for medications in patients with renal impairment, and drug interactions in prescription and focusing on those aged 18 and above. The most prescribed drugs include antihypertensives, antidiabetic, diuretics, and antibiotics. The findings highlight the significance of individualized treatment approaches in optimizing therapeutic success while minimizing potential hazards. We should focus on increased number of prescribed medications and co- morbidities to maintain appropriate doses of medicines. Dosages of medications cleared by the kidneys should be modified based on creatinine clearance or glomerular filtration rate and estimated using the Cockcroft gault equation. Renal failure has an impact on more than simply how medications and/ or active drug metabolites are handled by the kidneys. More study and collaboration among healthcare experts could result in better medication management guidelines for patients with renal impairment.

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